

THE EFFECT of LIGNOCAINE JELLY on a CUFF of an ENDOTRACHEAL TUBE on THE POSTOPERATIVE SORE THROAT : A PROSPECTIVE RANDOMISED STUDY.

NIKHIL KORDE ,RAHUL MAMDE,H.S.RAWAT

DEPARTMENT OF ANESTHESIOLOGY, DVVPF MEDICAL COLLEGE AHMEDNAGAR

Abstract

Background: Postoperative sore throat (POST) after general anesthesia with endotracheal intubation is present in mostly patients. We hypothesized that lignocaine jelly applied to the cuff of the endotracheal tube (ETT) might decrease the incidence of POST most commonly arising from endotracheal intubation.

Methods: A total of 104 patients under general anesthesia were randomly assigned into 1 of 2 groups. In the lidocaine group (n= 52), the distal part of ETTs with tapered-shaped cuff was lubricated with lidocaine jelly. In the control group (n=52), the distal part of ETTs with tapered-shaped cuff was lubricated with normal saline. The incidence of POST, hoarseness, and cough in the post anesthesia patients was compared.

Results: The overall incidence of POST was higher in the lignocaine group than in the normal saline group [30 (57%) vs 20 (38%), P=.006]. The incidence of POST at 1 hour postoperatively was higher in the lignocaine group than in the normal saline group [27(51%) vs 16 (31%), P=.003]. The overall incidence of hoarseness for 24hours postoperatively was comparable (P=.487). The overall incidence of cough for 24hours postoperatively is higher in the lidocaine group (P=.045).

Conclusion: The lignocaine jelly applied at the ETT with cuff increased the overall incidence of POST in patients undergoing general anesthesia.

Abbreviations: CI = confidence interval, ETT = endotracheal tube, POST = postoperative sore throat.

Keywords: gels, intubation, lignocaine, pain, pharyngitis, postoperative

1. Introduction

Postoperative sore throat (POST) is a most common and side effect of a general anesthesia.[1,2] This complication may impact quality of life.[3,4] The incidence of POST is known to be vary, with a range of 7% to 90%.[1,4,5] Preventive management of POST is recommended to improve the quality of postoperative care.[6] Local anesthetics have been implemented for the prophylaxis in an effort to decrease the incidence, or intensity and duration of POST.[1] Lignocaine has been used, both intravenously and topically, in an effort to prevent POST.[4,11] A conventional endotracheal tube (ETT) has a cylindrical.[12,13] The incidence of POST varies, depending upon the type of ETT implemented at the time of surgery. Moreover, there has been no investigation as to the effects (or potential benefit) of lignocaine jelly when it has been applied to an ETT cuff, in diminishing or obviating POST. We hypothesized that lignocaine jelly, applied on the cuff of ETT, might and probably could reduce the incidence, severity, and duration of POST emanating from endotracheal intubation.

2. Methods

2.1. Study Population

After obtaining the Institutional Ethics Committee approval, written informed consent was obtained from each patient. This was a prospective, randomized, double-blind, single-center, placebo-controlled, and parallel group study. A total of 104 patients were recruited to participate. The patients were of American Society of Anesthesiologists Physical Status I and II, aged 18 to 80 years, and were scheduled to undergo under general anesthesia. Patients with any history of pre-existing sore throat, recent upper respiratory infection, asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, chronic cough, friable teeth, concurrent, incidental use of lignocaine and dexamethasone, recent nonsteroidal anti inflammatory drug medication intake, presence of a gastric tube, previous head or neck surgery, anticipated difficulty with intubation, Mallampati grade>2, rapid sequence induction, more than one attempt at intubation, or known allergies to lignocaine jelly were excluded from this study.

2.2. Study Procedures and Anesthesia

Patients were randomly assigned to 1 of 2 groups: the lignocaine group and normal saline group. Randomization was performed using by Random sampling and was sequenced. The assignments were concealed in opaque envelopes and opened immediately before induction by a nurse who was unaware of the investigation protocol and responsible for preparing the ETT and study drugs. In the lidocaine group, the ETTs with cuff from the distal tip to the distal vocal cords marker were lubricated with lignocaine jelly (LOX 2%). In the control group, the ETTs with cuff from the distal tip to the distal vocal cords marker were lubricated with normal saline. The patients were monitored with electrocardiography, noninvasive blood pressure, pulse oximetry, etCO₂. Anesthesia was induced with propofol 2mg/kg and fentanyl 2 mcg/kg. Rocuronium 0.6 to 0.8mg/kg was administered to facilitate endotracheal intubation. An ETT with a cuff was inserted by an experienced anesthesiologist. Blinding group allocation was impossible because the nature of lubricants is different from that of normal saline. ETTs of internal diameter 7.0 and 7.5 were used for females and males, respectively. Direct laryngoscopy with either a Macintosh 3 or 4 laryngoscope blade was used for intubation. The ETT was inserted so that the vocal cords were located between the 2 indicator marks on the distal part of the tube shaft. Successful intubation was confirmed by end-tidal capnography. The tracheal tube cuff was inflated with air. The pressure of ETT cuff was maintained 20mm Hg throughout the surgery. Anesthesia was maintained with isoflurane inhalation. After induction injection paracetamol (10mg/kg) given for pain management was administered in both groups. After the surgery, glycopyrrolate 0.01mg/kg and neostigmine 0.05 mg/kg were infused to reverse residual neuromuscular relaxation. Oropharyngeal suction was gently performed under direct vision to avoid trauma to the tissues before extubation. Extubation of ETT was performed when adequate spontaneous breathing and response to verbal commands were confirmed. After extubation, patients were transferred to the post anesthesia care unit.

2.3. Outcomes Measurements

The Cormack and Lehane grade for laryngoscopic view assessment were recorded by the investigator performing tracheal intubation. The time-to-intubation was measured as the duration between inserting the laryngoscope blade into the patient's mouth and checking the end-tidal CO₂ >30mm Hg. The mean arterial blood pressure and heart rate were measured immediately before intubation and 2minutes after intubation.

The incidences of sore throat and hoarseness were monitored by a “blind” investigator at 1, 6, 12, and 24hours postoperatively. Sore throat was assessed at rest. Sore throat was graded on a 4-point scale (0–3): 0, no sore throat; 1, mild sore throat (complains of sore throat only on asking); 2, moderate sore throat (complains of sore throat on his/her own); and 3, severe sore throat (change in voice or hoarseness, associated with throat pain).

Hoarseness was graded on a 4-point scale (0–3): 0, No complaint of hoarseness; 1, minimal hoarseness (minimal change in quality of speech of which patient answers in the affirmative only when asked); 2, moderate hoarseness (moderate change in quality of speech of which the patient complains on his/her own); 3, severe hoarseness (gross change in the quality of voice perceived by the observer).

Postoperative cough was graded on a 4-point scale (0–3): 0, No cough; 1, mild cough; 2, moderate cough; 3, severe cough.[15]

The primary endpoint was the incidence of POST between groups during 24hours postoperatively. Secondary endpoints were the incidence of POST and hoarseness at postoperative 1, 6, 12, and 24hours postoperatively, as well as cough, throat numbness, nausea, vomiting, and use of additional analgesics during 24hours postoperatively.

2.4. Statistical Analysis

A previous study demonstrated that the incidence of POST was about 36% during 24 hours following the intubation with ETT of tapered-shaped cuff.[16] Assuming that this incidence would decrease to 18% in the lidocaine group, 47 patients would be required in each group to reach statistical significance with $\alpha=0.05$ and $\beta=0.20$. Considering a 10% dropout rate and a 100% compliance rate, 52 patients per group were included. Statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics software (ver. 22.0; IBM CORP., Armonk, NY). The incidence of POST, hoarseness, cough, throat numbness, nausea, vomiting, and the use of additional analgesics were assessed using the Chi square test, or if there were 5 values per cell, the Fisher exact test. Continuous variables were compared using Student t test after a normality test. The alpha value was adjusted with Bonferroni correction to compare the POST and pain score between the 2 groups at each time point. The P values were compared to adjust alpha values. Otherwise, a P value $<.05$ was considered to indicate a significant difference. Data are presented as mean standard deviation or number (percentage).

3. Results

A total of 104 patient . There were no differences in the patient characteristics between the groups (Table 1).

The overall incidence of POST was higher in the lignocaine group than in the normal saline group [30 (57%) vs 20 (38%), $P=.006$, Table 2, Fig. 2]. The incidence of POST at 1hour postoperatively was higher in the lignocaine group than in the normal saline group ($P=.003$). The incidence of POST at postoperative 6, 12, and 24hours was comparable between groups. The overall incidence of hoarseness for 24 hours postoperatively was comparable [29 (56%) vs 27 (52%), $P=.487$]. The incidence of hoarseness was similar at postoperative 1, 6, 12, and 24hours between the lidocaine and normal saline group ($P=.567$, $P=.544$, $P=.354$, and $P=.092$, respectively). The overall incidence of cough (during the course of the entire investigation) was higher in the lidocaine group than in the normal saline group [14 (27%) vs 08 (15%), $P=.045$]. The incidence of cough at postoperative 1 hour is higher in the lignocaine group than in the normal saline group ($P=.002$). The incidence of cough was comparable at postoperative 6, 12, and 24hours between the lidocaine and normal saline group ($P=.810$, $P=.561$, and $P=.043$, respectively). The incidence of postoperative nausea [25 (24%) vs 30 (29%), difference 5%, $P=.432$], vomiting [7 (7%) vs 8 (8%), $P=.789$], and throat numbness [15 (14%) vs 11 (11%), $P=.402$] during the study period was comparable between the lidocaine and normal saline group.

4. Discussion

This investigation demonstrated that the lignocaine jelly applied at the distal part of ETT with cuff increased the overall incidence of POST. The lignocaine jelly also increased the incidence of cough compared with the normal saline at postoperative 1hour. The incidence of POST is influenced by many factors such as ETT cuff design and pressure, intubation procedure, movement of ETT during surgery, coughing on the ETT, and pharyngeal suctioning during extubation.[14,17,18]The proposed mechanism of POST is thought to be an inflammation through injury of the pharyngeal and tracheal mucosa by traumatic laryngoscopy and contact with the ETT cuff.[3,19–21] Lidocaine with analgesic and anti-inflammatory effect may be optimal choice for the prevention of POST after general anesthesia with ETT intubation. Previous investigations have shown that topical application of lidocaine reduced the incidence of POST.[4,10,22] Lignocaine jelly among various topical application methods, however, have shown equivocal results in terms of pro-active POST prevention.[4,10]

Table 1: Patients & anesthetic characteristics

	LIGNOCAINE(n=52)	NORMAL SALINE (n=52)	P
Age, years	58+ 15	56+ 16	0.446
Female/male	35/17	31/21	0.194
Weight, kg	63+ 11	65+ 11	0.171
Height, cm	160+ 9	161+ 8	0.259
Body mass index, kg/m2	24.5+ 3.8	24.9+ 3.7	0.239
ASA-PS, I/II	25/27	27/25	0.488
Time to intubation, sec	18+ 11	18+ 10	0.584
Duration of tracheal intubation, min	68+ 46	62+ 39	0.976
Mallampati grade, I/II	16/36	21/31	0.148
C-L grading scale, I/II/III	14/30/8	16/27/9	0.820
Mean arterial pressure, mm Hg			
Before intubation	79+ 14	80+ 13	0.773
2min after intubation	98+ 19	101+ 22	0.489
Heart rate, beats/min			
Before intubation	76+ 14	74+ 13	0.144
2min after intubation	92+ 16	92+ 21	0.741

Table 2 : Incidence and severity of postoperative sore throat, hoarseness, and cough

	Lignocaine (n=52)	Normal saline (n=52)	P
Sore throat			
Overall incidence	30(57%)	20(38%)	0.006
Postoperative 1 h (none/mild/moderate/severe)	25/21/4/2	36/13/2/1	0.003
Postoperative 6 h (none/mild/moderate/severe)	35/14/2/1	42/8/1/1	0.041
Postoperative 12 h(none/mild/moderate/severe)	43/8/0/1	44/7/1/0	0.849
Postoperative 24 h(none/mild/moderate/severe)	48/3/0/1	48/3/1/0	0.789
Hoarseness			
Overall incidence	29(56%)	27(52%)	0.487
Postoperative 1 h (none/mild/moderate/severe)	33/15/3/1	31/17/4/0	0.567
Postoperative 6 h (none/mild/moderate/severe)	37/13/1/1	35/15/2/0	0.544
Postoperative 12h(none/mild/moderate/severe)	44/7/0/1	42/10/0/0	0.354
Postoperative 24h(none/mild/moderate/severe)	49/2/0/1	45/6/1/0	0.92
Cough			
Overall incidence	14(27%)	08(15%)	0.045
Postoperative 1 h (none/mild/moderate/severe)	37/14/1/0	46/4/1/1	0.002
Postoperative 6 h (none/mild/moderate/severe)	47/5/0/0	48/4/0/0	0.810
Postoperative 12 h(none/mild/moderate/severe)	51/1/0/0	52/0/0/0	0.561
Postoperative 24 h(none/mild/moderate/severe)	50/2/0/0	52/0/0/0	0.043

Values are presented as the number (%) of patients.

In our study, lignocaine jelly applied on the ETT with cuff increased the incidence of POST by 20% at 1 hour postoperatively. This deleterious effect of lignocaine jelly at early post operative period may increase the overall incidence of POST by 23%. The lignocaine jelly in our investigation contains several agents such as chlorhexidine gluconate, methylhydroxybenzoate, and propylhydroxybenzoate for antiseptic effect. Chlorhexidine gluconate can

cause hypersensitivity reactions.[23] Methyl hydroxybenzoate and propyl hydroxy benzoate are chemical allergens that may induce allergic dermatitis. [24,25] Such additive agents for the prevention of infection may be irritative to the upper airway of patients. The additive agents including methylhydroxybenzoate and propylhydroxy benzoate may form the dry sediments. Such sediments in the patients' trachea may irritate the airway and increase cough and POST. The chemical and mechanical irritation by additive agents may increase the incidence of POST in our investigation. Postoperative cough can increase complications, including bronchospasm, hypertension, cardiac disease, bleeding, bronchospasm, increased intraocular and intracranial pressure, and postoperative surgical complications.[10,26,27] These complications can result in hypoxemia, myocardial ischemia, and brain injury.[28,29]Development of a cough after general anesthesia may be due to irritation and inflammation of respiratory tract by ETT.[4] Topical application of lignocaine to soothen the respiratory tract mucosa may represent a reasonable, pro-active means of preventing post-ETT cough.[30]As well, ETT cuff design and ETT lubricants have been known to influence the incidence and severity of post operative cough.[31]The cuff of ETT may enhance the effect of topical agents by keeping the agents at the level of the contact area between ETT and respiratory mucosa. Previous investigation demonstrated that lignocaine jelly applied on the ETT with barrel-shaped cuff prevents cough at immediate postoperative period.[4] In our investigation using ETT with cuff, however, the incidence of cough at early postoperative period was higher in the lignocaine group by 17% than the normal saline group. This deleterious effect of lignocaine jelly at early postoperative period may increase the overall incidence of cough by 12%. The chemical and mechanical irritation by additives in lidocaine jelly may be enhanced by the cuff of ETT. There is a relationship between the frequency of cough and that of POST.[10] In our investigation, the incidence of POST and cough is higher in the lidocaine group at the immediate postoperative period. Cough is thought to increase the injury of the tracheal mucosa, which is associated with POST.[32] The higher incidence of cough in lignocaine group may contribute to the higher incidence of POST in our investigation. The implementation of intravenous lignocaine, lignocaine spray applied to the pharyngeal structure, and intra-cuff lignocaine has been studied for the prevention of POST. Intravenous lignocaine increases the time from the conclusion of surgery to removal of the ETT.[10] Systemic lignocaine may also increase the risk of cardiovascular and central nervous system toxicity.[33] Lignocaine spray applied to the oral pharyngeal cavity increases the incidence of POST.[34] Lignocaine spray applied 10minutes before intubation decreases the incidence of POST.[35] It, however, may increase the preparation time of anesthesia. Intra-cuff lignocaine is effective for the prevention of POST. Intra-cuff lignocaine would, theoretically, reduce or obviate chemical irritation from the additives.[8] It was, however, impossible to inflate the cuff of ETT using liquid agents such as normal saline or lignocaine in our in vivo experiment. In that regards, topical agents to prevent POST would be necessary for those patients undergoing general anesthesia using ETT. Further investigations of the use of topical agents (including lignocaine) without irritative agents or benzydamine are necessary. The incidence of POST in our investigation was similar with our previous study.[16] The incidence of POST is highest at 1 hour postoperatively in both groups. Previous investigation using ETT with cylindrical-shaped cuff showed that the incidence of POST is the highest at 6hours after extubation.[8] Anesthetic protocol, types of surgery, and the design of the ETT cuff could influence such a difference in timing of the highest incidence of POST. In the previous investigation,[8] propofol was used as an anesthetic maintenance agent. In our study protocol, isoflurane was used instead. The duration of procedure was relatively shorter in our study than that in the previous research.[8] ETT with cuff was inserted in our study.[8] Such factors may cause the difference in timing of the highest incidence of POST. Future investigation is necessary to evaluate the relationship among POST, anesthetic agents, the type of surgery, and the type of the ETT cuff. The current investigation had some limitations. First, variables such as sore throat and hoarseness are subjective. POST may be affected by airway management including extubation and oral suctioning. The attending anesthesiologists and the investigator who measured outcome were "blind" to minimize bias. Second, it is impossible to blind the investigator who intubated patients because of the different nature between lignocaine jelly and normal saline. Further investigation using lubricants without irritative agents in the control group may be necessary. The bias was minimized by blinding the investigator who measured postoperative outcomes. Third, coughing on the tube was not measured. Bucking and coughing at emergence from anesthesia is known to increase POST.[4] Future study may be necessitated to evaluate the association with lignocaine jelly and cough on the tube. Fourth, postoperative wound pain was not measured. Wound pain may affect the incidence and severity of POST. The bias by this factor could be minimized by randomization.

5. Conclusion

This investigation found the deleterious effect of using the lignocaine jelly on the cuff of ETT for patients under general anesthesia. The lignocaine jelly applied at the distal part of ETT with cuff increased the overall incidence of POST and cough in patients undergoing surgery with general anaesthesia. The lignocaine jelly containing irritative chemical additives should therefore not be recommended for the prophylactic prevention of POST after general anesthesia, especially using ETT with cuff.

References

- [1] Tanaka Y, Nakayama T, Nishimori M, et al. Lidocaine for preventing postoperative sore throat. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* 2015;7: CD004081.
- [2] Macario A, Weinger M, Carney S, et al. Which clinical anesthesia outcomes are important to avoid? The perspective of patients. *Anesth Analg* 1999;89:652–8.
- [3] Park SH, Han SH, Do SH, et al. Prophylactic dexamethasone decreases the incidence of sore throat and hoarseness after tracheal extubation with a double-lumen endobronchial tube. *Anesth Analg* 2008;107:1814–8.
- [4] Sumathi PA, Shenoy T, Ambareesha M, et al. Controlled comparison between betamethasone gel and lidocaine jelly applied over tracheal tube to reduce postoperative sore throat, cough, and hoarseness of voice. *Br J Anaesth* 2008;100:215–8.
- [5] Maruyama K, Sakai H, Miyazawa H, et al. Sore throat and hoarseness after total intravenous anaesthesia. *Br J Anaesth* 2004;92:541–3.
- [6] Monem A, Kamal RS. Postoperative sore throat. *J Coll Physicians Surg Pak* 2007;17:509–14.
- [7] Navarro RM, Baughman VL. Lidocaine in the endotracheal tube cuff reduces postoperative sore throat. *J Clin Anesth* 1997;9:394–7.
- [8] Hung NK, Wu CT, Chan SM, et al. Effect on postoperative sore throat of spraying the endotracheal tube cuff with benzydamine hydrochloride, 10% lidocaine, and 2% lidocaine. *Anesth Analg* 2010;111:882–6.
- [9] Mekhemar NA, El-Agwany AS, Radi WK, et al. Comparative study between benzydamine hydrochloride gel, lidocaine 5% gel and lidocaine 10% spray on endotracheal tube cuff as regards postoperative sore throat. *Braz J Anesthesiol* 2016;66:242–8.
- [10] Soltani HA, Aghadavoudi O. The effect of different lidocaine application methods on postoperative cough and sore throat. *J Clin Anesth* 2002;14:15–8.
- [11] Mekhemar NA, El-Agwany AS, Radi WK, et al. [Comparative study between benzydamine hydrochloride gel, lidocaine 5% gel and lidocaine 10% spray on endotracheal tube cuff as regards postoperative sore throat]. *Rev Bras Anesthesiol* 2016;66:242–8.
- [12] Dave MH, Frotzler A, Spielmann N, et al. Effect of tracheal tube cuff shape on fluid leakage across the cuff: an in vitro study. *Br J Anaesth* 2010;105:538–43.
- [13] Zanella A, Scaravilli V, Isgro S, et al. Fluid leakage across tracheal tube cuff, effect of different cuff material, shape, and positive expiratory pressure: a bench-top study. *Intensive Care Med* 2011;37:343–7.
- [14] Mandoeh, Nikolajsen L, Lintrup U, et al. Sore throat after endotracheal intubation. *Anesth Analg* 1992;74:897–900.
- [15] Harding CJ, McVey FK. Interview method affects incidence of postoperative sore throat. *Anaesthesia* 1987;42:1104–7.
- [16] Kim HC, Lee YH, Kim E, et al. Comparison of the endotracheal tube cuff pressure between a tapered- versus a cylindrical-shaped cuff after changing from the supine to the lateral flank position. *Can J Anaesth* 2015;62:1063–70.
- [17] McHardy FE, Chung F. Postoperative sore throat: cause, prevention and treatment. *Anaesthesia* 1999;54:444–53.
- [18] Narimani M, Seyed Mehdi SA, Gholami F, et al. The effect of betamethasone gel and lidocaine jelly applied over tracheal tube cuff on postoperative sore throat, cough, and hoarseness. *J Perianesth Nurs* 2016;31:298–302.
- [19] Huang YS, Hung NK, Lee MS, et al. The effectiveness of benzydamine hydrochloride spraying on the endotracheal tube cuff or oral mucosa for postoperative sore throat. *Anesth Analg* 2010;111:887–91.
- [20] Jones MW, Catling S, Evans E, et al. Hoarseness after tracheal intubation. *Anaesthesia* 1992;47:213–6.
- [21] Thomas DV. Hoarseness and sore throat after tracheal intubation. Small tubes prevent. *Anaesthesia* 1993;48:355–6.
- [22] Lam F, Lin YC, Tsai HC, et al. Effect of intracuff lidocaine on postoperative sore throat and the emergence phenomenon: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *PLoS One* 2015;10:e0136184.
- [23] Parkes AW, Harper N, Herwadkar A, et al. Anaphylaxis to the chlorhexidine component of Instillagel: a case series. *Br J Anaesth* 2009;102:65–8.
- [24] Schamberg IL. Allergic contact dermatitis to methyl and propyl paraben. *Arch Dermatol* 1967;95:626–8.
- [25] Schorr WF. Paraben allergy. A cause of intractable dermatitis. *JAMA* 1968;204:859–62.
- [26] Wetzell LE, Ancona AL, Cooper AS, et al. The effectiveness of 4% intracuff lidocaine in reducing coughing during emergence from general anesthesia in smokers undergoing procedures lasting less than 1.5 hours. *AANA J* 2008;76:105–8.
- [27] Souissi H, Frechette Y, Murza A, et al. Intracuff 160mg alkalized lidocaine reduces cough upon emergence from N2O-free general anesthesia: a randomized controlled trial. *Can J Anaesth* 2016;63: 862–70. [28] Leech P, Barker J, Fitch W. Proceedings: changes in intracranial pressure and systemic arterial pressure during the termination of anaesthesia. *Br J Anaesth* 1974; 46:315–316.

- [29] Bidwai AV, Bidwai VA, Rogers CR, et al. Blood-pressure and pulse-rate responses to endotracheal extubation with and without prior injection of lidocaine. *Anesthesiology* 1979;51:171-3.
- [30] Gonzalez RM, Bjerke RJ, Drobycki T, et al. Prevention of endotracheal tube-induced coughing during emergence from general anesthesia. *Anesth Analg* 1994;79:792-5.
- [31] Loeser EA, Kaminsky A, Diaz A, et al. The influence of endotracheal tube cuff design and cuff lubrication on postoperative sore throat. *Anesthesiology* 1983;58:376-9.
- [32] Combes X, Schavvliege F, Peyrouset O, et al. Intracuff pressure and tracheal morbidity: influence of filling with saline during nitrous oxide anesthesia. *Anesthesiology* 2001;95:1120-4.
- [33] Wolfe JW, Butterworth JF. Local anesthetic systemic toxicity: update on mechanisms and treatment. *Curr Opin Anaesthesiol* 2011;24: 561-6. [34] Maruyama K, Sakai H, Miyazawa H, et al. Laryngotracheal application of lidocaine spray increases the incidence of postoperative sore throat after total intravenous anesthesia. *J Anesth* 2004;18:237-40.
- [35] Honma K, Kamachi M, Akamatsu Y, et al. Lidocaine spray 10 min prior to intubation: effects on postoperative sore throat. *J Anesth* 2010; 24:962-5.